

Hyperparameter Sets for Comparing Load-Forecasts of Residential Heatpumps with Transformer and XGBoost on Field Data

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Table 1 Hyperparameters Search Range for XGB, with final Parameter being underlined

Hyperparameter	Description	Range
n_estimators	Number of decision trees to be trained	100, 200, 300, 500, 700, <u>1000</u>
learning rate	Contribution of each tree to the final prediction	0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08, 0.1, <u>0.2</u> , 0.3
gamma	Minimum loss reduction required to make a further partition on a leaf node	0.02, <u>0.05</u> , 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, 0.5, 1
max_depth	Maximum depth of a tree	2, 3, 4, 5, <u>6</u> , 8, 10
min_child_weight	Minimum sum of instance weight (hessian) needed in a child	1, 3, 5, <u>7</u>
colsample_bytree	Fraction of features to be subsampled for each tree	0.3, 0.5, <u>0.7</u> , 0.9, 1.0
subsample	Fraction of training instances to be randomly sampled for each tree	0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, <u>1.0</u>
lambda	L2 regularization term on weights	<u>0.1</u> , 0.2, 0.5, 0.8, 1.1, 2

Table 2 Hyperparameter selection for a basic Transformer model

Hyperparameter	Description	Value
src_input_size	Dimension of encoder input variables (features and target)	15
tgt_input_size	Dimension of decoder input variables	14
d_model	Dimension of the model	32
nhead	Number of multi-head attention heads	2
num_encoder_layers	Number of encoder layers	1
num_decoder_layers	Number of decoder layers	1
dim_feedforward	Dimension of the feed-forward network (FFN)	8
dropout	Dropout probability	0.1434
layer_norm_eps	Epsilon value for layer normalization	1×10^{-5}
Batch size	Number of training samples per iteration	128

Table 3 Hyperparameter selection for the optimized Transformer model

Hyperparameter	Description	Range
d_model	Dimension of the model	16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512
nhead	Number of multi-head attention heads	Integers from 1 to 8
num_encoder_layers	Number of encoder layers	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6
num_decoder_layers	Number of decoder layers	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6
dim_feedforward	Dimension of the feed-forward network (FFN)	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
dropout	Dropout rate for regularization	0.0 to 0.4
learning_rate	Learning rate for the optimizer	$1e-5$ to $5e-3$ (logarithmic)
batch_size	Number of training samples per iteration	8, 16, 32, 64, 128

Table 4 Comparison of optimized hyperparameters for various Transformer models

Hyperparameter	EOH2504	EOH0793	EOH1700
d_model	16	16	16
nhead	1	8	4
num_encoder_layers	4	2	4
num_decoder_layers	6	3	6
dim_feedforward	128	32	128
dropout	0.012	0.027	0.091
layer_norm_eps	1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-5}
learning_rate	0.0023	0.00099	0.000542
batch_size	8	128	64
src_input_size	15	15	15
tgt_input_size	14	14	14

Table 5 Impact of features on load forecasting results for EOH2504 based on R^2

Feature Analysis	XGB	Transf.
Feature analysis	0.836	0.77
Excluding historical load	-0.03	-0.03
Excluding temp. and lagged	0.812	0.76
Excluding Sine and Cosine	0.831	0.77
Historical load only	0.789	0.76
Same hour (7d lag) only	0.754	0.69
Temperature only	-0.04	-0.03
All features	0.834	0.78